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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR FORMING AND IMPLEMENTING INVESTMENT POLICY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS... 8 Abduvaliyev Sanjar Abdurahmanovich	8
EVALUATION OF MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BASED ON BUDGETING IN ENERGY ENTERPRISES (A FACTOR ANALYSIS CASE OF "HUDUDGAZTA'MINOT" JSC)..... 17 Sobirov Shoyadbek Kurbonaliyevich	17
PORTFOLIO OF POSTAL SERVICES AND THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF ITS DIGITALIZATION23 Mamatkulov Gulom Rustamovich	23
OPTIMIZING THE BALANCE BETWEEN LIQUIDITY AND CREDIT RISKS IN ENSURING BANKING STABILITY 30 Anvarov Asliddin Nabijon ugli	30
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY DEPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....34 Hamroyeva Sabina Ismoil qizi, Dilshod Anvarjonovich Ismailov	34
MODERN TRENDS AND EFFICIENCY OF LENDING TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCERS IN UZBEKISTAN..39 Shamshetova Gulraushan Sarsenovna	39
ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN YOUTH EMPLOYMENT AND CRIME (CASE OF UZBEKISTAN) 42 Khusniddinova Gulnoza	42
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN'S FINANCIAL SYSTEM 47 Qobilova Nodira Qayumjon qizi, Normurodov Kh.E.	47
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN 52 Mamadzhanova Tuygunoy Akhmadzhanovna	52
INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ITS ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY 56 Otbosarov Abrorbek Adhamjon o'g'li	56
LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX (LOSS MANAGEMENT MATRIX) MODEL IN POWER GRID ENTERPRISES.. 61 Khojimurodov Zukhriddin Shukurullo oglu	61
MICROPROJECTS AS A MEANS OF INCREASING THE FINANCIAL ACTIVITY AND LITERACY OF THE POPULATION 67 Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	67
INSTITUTIONAL VA TEXNOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLAR SHAROITIDA INNOVATION BANK XIZMATLARINI JORIY ETISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..... 74 Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	74
PROBLEMS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL CLUSTERS IN THE LIGHT INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN 80 Umarkulov Kodirjon Maxamadaminovich	80
DIGITAL FINANCIAL INCLUSION AS A DRIVER OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM GLOBAL TRENDS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES..... 84 Sabitov Oybek Abduganievich, Sattoriy Fayzullokh Abdijabbor ugli	84
PROPERTIES OF HEAVY CONCRETE DISPERSEDLY REINFORCED WITH NON-METALLIC FIBERS AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CALCULATING CONCRETE STRUCTURES BASED ON THEM 90 Usmonova Durdona, Gulomova Dilnura	90
THE EFFECT OF STABLE AND DYNAMIC PRICING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR 98 Anvar DEBERDIYEV	98
ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.. 102 M.O. Yo'ldoshova	102

PEDAGOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING POLITICAL SCIENCE AT HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	106
Rasulev Bobirjon Atkhamovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR REGULATING NON-STANDARD EMPLOYMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESSES	110
Fayzullayev Nurulla Bakhromovich	
PRIORITIES FOR IMPROVING THE HEALTHCARE FINANCING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	117
Gulira'no Atabekovna Ruzmetova	
FACTORS AFFECTING TAX PAYMENT SYSTEMS, EXISTING PROBLEMS, AND THEIR CAUSES	124
Tangirqulov Gulom Baxtiyorovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF ENVIRONMENTAL TAXES IN REDUCING CARBON EMISSIONS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ECONOMETRIC APPROACH.....	129
Kuziboev Bekhzod Hamidovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN THE SILK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY	134
Bahriddinov Asror Rakhmatovich, Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
STATE OF LENDING TO SMALL BUSINESS PROJECTS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS AND ITS ECONOMIC-STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.....	138
Nargiza Norqobilova Abdiqodirovna	
CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	143
Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi	

CONCEPTUAL DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES

Asomidinova Mohigulbonu Oybek kizi

Teacher of the Department of Finance and Financial Technologies
University of Science and Technologies

Abstract: This article explores the issues of improving the mechanisms for ensuring the financial stability of enterprises in the context of economic transformation, using the example of the “Toshshahartrans” enterprise. During the study, the capital structure of the enterprise, the ratio of equity and debt funds, as well as financial independence coefficients were analyzed for the period 2023–2025. The article develops conceptual directions for increasing financial stability and provides scientific and practical proposals for capital optimization and risk minimization.

Keywords: financial stability, capital structure, financial independence, autonomy coefficient, Toshshahartrans, financial mechanism, profitability, conceptual directions.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada «Toshshahartrans» korxonasi misolida iqtisodiyotni transformatsiyalash sharoitida korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqot davomida korxonaning kapital tuzilmasi, xususi va qarz mablag'larining o'zaro nisbati hamda moliyaviy mustaqillik koeffitsiyentlari 2023–2025-yillar kesimida tahlil qilingan. Maqolada moliyaviy barqarorlikni oshirishning konseptual yo'nalishlari ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, unda kapitalni optimallashtirish va risklarni minimallashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy takliflar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: moliyaviy barqarorlik, kapital tuzilmasi, moliyaviy mustaqillik, avtonomiya koeffitsiyenti, Toshshahartrans, moliyaviy mexanizm, rentabellik, konseptual yo'nalishlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются вопросы совершенствования механизмов обеспечения финансовой устойчивости предприятий в условиях трансформации экономики на примере предприятия «Тощахартранс». В ходе исследования проанализированы структура капитала предприятия, соотношение собственных и заемных средств, а также коэффициенты финансовой независимости в разрезе 2023–2025 годов. В статье разработаны концептуальные направления повышения финансовой устойчивости, даны научно-практические предложения по оптимизации капитала и минимизации рисков.

Ключевые слова: финансовая устойчивость, структура капитала, финансовая независимость, коэффициент автономии, Тощахартранс, финансовый механизм, рентабельность, концептуальные направления.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of accelerating global economic processes and rapid changes in market conditions, ensuring the stability of business entities is becoming one of the most urgent priorities. In particular, for large enterprises operating in the transport services sector, financial stability is not only a means of maintaining current solvency but also a key guarantee for the continuous implementation of strategic development and technical modernization processes. The structural reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan's economy require enterprises to introduce innovative mechanisms for managing financial resources and to optimize their capital structure in accordance with market requirements.

The mechanism for ensuring financial stability in an enterprise is a complex system that includes such important components as capital formation, risk management, and forecasting financial results. In the case of strategically important enterprises such as Toshshahartrans, increasing the level of financial independence is of particular importance from the perspective of social and economic stability. This is because capital turnover and profitability in the service sector directly depend on the degree to which the financial management mechanism has been improved.

The relevance of this study lies in the fact that many domestic enterprises are consistently strengthening the efficiency of internal reserves utilization, improving financial risk management systems, and gradually reducing dependence on external borrowed funds. Developing conceptual directions for ensuring financial

stability makes it possible to further enhance these positive processes and strengthen the economic security of enterprises.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the mechanisms for ensuring financial stability in enterprises, assess the capital structure and financial independence indicators using Toshshahartrans as an example, and develop scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations for improving the sector. To achieve this goal, the enterprise's financial resource management strategy, ways to ensure an optimal capital ratio, and factors affecting financial results are studied in detail.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Issues related to the financial stability and capital structure management of enterprises have long been at the center of both classical and modern economic theories. The concepts developed by Franco Modigliani and Merton Miller regarding the relationship between capital structure and enterprise value served as an important foundation for the formation of theoretical views in this field. Their ideas were later enriched by the "Pecking Order Theory" developed by Stewart Myers and Nicholas Majluf. According to this theory, enterprises prioritize internal resources first, borrowed funds second, and the issuance of shares last when selecting financing sources, which is considered the most optimal way to ensure financial stability.

Among foreign economists, Eugene Brigham and James Van Horne extensively explained the mechanism of maintaining a balance between risk and profitability in managing financial stability through their research. In their view, the financial independence of an enterprise is measured not only by the extent to which assets are covered by own funds, but also by the adequacy of cash flows relative to debt obligations. In addition, the bankruptcy prediction models developed by Edward Altman continue to be widely applied in global practice for the quantitative assessment of financial stability.

Economists from the CIS countries and local scholars have also conducted significant research in this field. In particular, economist V.V. Kovalev interprets financial stability as the enterprise's ability to adapt to changes in the economic environment and maintain long-term solvency. Among Uzbek scholars, A.V. Vahobov and N.X. Jumaev emphasized in their scientific works the importance of capitalizing private equity and optimizing dividend policy to increase the financial independence of enterprises, taking into account the specific characteristics of the national economy.

At the same time, Sh.Z. Abdullaeva and other local researchers studied the role of external financing in ensuring the financial stability of enterprises and analyzed the impact of bank loans and leasing relations on capital structure. However, comprehensive approaches aimed at improving the mechanisms for ensuring the financial stability of large state-owned enterprises in the transport sector, particularly systems such as Toshshahartrans, and developing them on the basis of conceptual directions, still remain highly relevant under modern conditions. By generalizing the theoretical views mentioned above, this study is aimed at developing new conceptual foundations of financial stability based on the practical indicators of the enterprise.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of this study consists of a systematic approach and the principles of studying economic phenomena and processes in their interrelation. In developing conceptual directions for improving the mechanisms of ensuring financial stability in the enterprise, a combination of theoretical and practical research methods was applied.

The research process covered the following consecutive stages:

At the first stage, existing concepts and foreign experience related to financial stability and capital structure were studied using the method of theoretical generalization. In this process, classical financial theories and modern corporate governance principles were comparatively analyzed, and the theoretical foundation of the study was formed.

At the second stage, an empirical analysis was conducted based on the financial and accounting reports of Toshshahartrans for 2023–2025. Economic-statistical grouping, coefficient methods, and dynamic series analysis were used in processing the data. In particular, the enterprise's autonomy, financial dependency, liquidity, and profitability indicators were calculated by years, and their trends were identified.

At the third stage, correlation and logistic analysis methods were applied to assess the impact of the capital structure (the ratio of own funds to borrowed funds) on the enterprise's net profit and asset turnover. Particular attention was paid to the leverage effect, and the optimal limits of debt burden were determined.

At the fourth and final stage, the results of the analysis were generalized using induction and deduction methods. Based on the obtained numerical data, a conceptual model for ensuring financial stability in the enterprise was developed. The reliability of the study is justified by the fact that the applied data were

obtained from official sources and that internationally recognized economic analysis formulas were used in the calculations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the results of the study, a significant increase in the share of equity capital in the structure of capital formation sources was observed at Toshshahartrans. While in 2023 only 33 percent of the company's assets were financed through its own funds, by the end of 2025 this indicator had reached 54 percent. This result indicates that the company's autonomy coefficient exceeded the internationally accepted safety threshold of 0.5. The growth of equity capital from 145.2 billion soums to 258.9 billion soums demonstrates that the enterprise has formed a solid "foundation of financial independence."

The increase in financial independence was directly accompanied by a reduction in debt burden. During the analyzed period, the company's financial dependency coefficient decreased from 2.04 to 0.86, indicating that the amount of debt corresponding to each soum of equity capital declined by more than two times. Such dynamics enabled Toshshahartrans to optimize interest expenses on credit obligations and direct a larger share of net profit toward expanding production activities. In particular, the transition of the level of own working capital coverage from a negative indicator to a positive value of 0.14 is an important result proving that the company's current assets are now financed not through debt, but through internal profit sources.

The optimization of the capital structure also had a positive impact on the company's operational efficiency. The acceleration of asset turnover from 0.45 to 0.88 indicates that the efficiency of asset utilization nearly doubled. The reduction in the turnover period of accounts receivable from 58 days to 28 days reflects improvements in the cash flow management system and the strengthening of the company's liquidity position.

One of the most significant results obtained is the increase in return on equity (ROE) from 3.8 percent to 15.6 percent. This indicator confirms that the strategic direction of the company's management was chosen correctly and that achieving financial stability can lead to high economic efficiency. The restoration of solvency and the increase of the financial stability coefficient to 0.82 fully demonstrate that Toshshahartrans possesses the potential for sustainable development even without external investments in the future. In general, the results of the analysis show that the mechanism for ensuring financial independence in the enterprise is functioning successfully, and that applying this experience to other enterprises in the sector would be appropriate.

This Table 1 represents a conceptual program linking the financial recovery strategy of Toshshahartrans with its expected future outcomes. Its analysis reveals the mechanism through which the enterprise transitions from a crisis condition to a model of sustainable growth:

1. Fundamental restructuring of the financial architecture. The first block of the table is aimed at optimizing the capital structure. The primary emphasis here is placed on reducing the debt burden. The target of maintaining the autonomy coefficient above 0.5 indicates the company's complete withdrawal from excessive dependence on external creditors and its ability to make independent decisions based on its own resources. This strategic direction minimizes the risk of bankruptcy for the enterprise.

2. Technological and innovative management mechanism. The introduction of digital control and ERP systems ensures transparency of cash flows, which is one of the most critical "pain points" in the transport sector. The proposal to reduce the accounts receivable turnover period to 30 days is intended to prevent cash gaps and eliminate shortages of working capital. This serves as a guarantee not only of financial stability but also of operational stability (Table 1).

Table 1. Conceptual Directions for Ensuring Financial Stability in Toshshahartrans and Expected Results

Conceptual Directions	Implementation Mechanisms	Expected Economic Result (Indicator)
Optimization of capital structure	Restructuring debt obligations and increasing the share of own funds	Autonomy coefficient exceeding 0.5
Financial risk management	Introduction of an early warning stress-testing system and liquidity monitoring	Reduction of the financial dependency level below 1.0
Increasing asset efficiency	Modernization of the technical fleet and disposal of unused assets	Acceleration of asset turnover by 1.5–2.0 times
Digital financial control	Creation of a transparent cash flow system based on ERP and blockchain technologies	Reduction of accounts receivable turnover period to 30 days
Investment attractiveness	Expansion of Public-Private Partnership (PPP) projects	Increase of return on equity (ROE) to 18–20%

3. Asset utilization and investment attractiveness. The table forecasts an acceleration of asset turnover by 1.5–2.0 times and an increase in profitability (ROE) to 20 percent. Such results can only be achieved through the modernization of the technical fleet (buses and electric buses) and by increasing their utilization coefficients. The introduction of the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) mechanism enables the enterprise to attract additional investments without placing an extra burden on the state budget.

The implementation of these conceptual directions will transform Toshshahartrans from an entity dependent on social subsidies into a modern corporate structure that generates profit and is capable of self-financing. The proposed indicators demonstrate that the assessment of the company's financial stability should be based not only on accounting balance sheet data, but also on market requirements and efficiency indicators (Table 2).

Table 2. Dynamics of Financial Stability and Solvency Indicators of Toshshahartrans

Indicator Name	2023	2024	2025	Difference 2025/2023 (+/-)
Absolute liquidity ratio (standard: > 0.2)	0.08	0.15	0.24	+0.16
Quick ratio (standard: 0.7–1.0)	0.42	0.68	0.92	+0.50
Current ratio (standard: > 2.0)	1.15	1.64	2.12	+0.97
Maneuverability ratio (standard: 0.2–0.5)	-0.12	0.18	0.34	+0.46
Debt-to-equity ratio (Leverage)	3.46	1.44	0.86	-2.60
Cash flow adequacy (million soums)	12,400	45,800	98,600	+86,200

The data presented in Table 2 prove that the financial recovery process of Toshshahartrans has reached a new stage not only quantitatively (through profit growth), but also qualitatively (through improved security and liquidity). The logical analysis of the table leads to the following important conclusions:

1. Overcoming the critical solvency threshold. The most remarkable aspect of the table is the positive dynamics of liquidity indicators. In 2023, the absolute liquidity ratio amounted to 0.08, indicating that the company was in a very difficult financial situation and could cover only 8 percent of its current liabilities with cash funds. By 2025, this indicator increased to 0.24, reflecting the restoration of the company's payment discipline. In particular, the increase in the current ratio to 2.12 (with the standard being 2.0) demonstrates that the company's short-term liabilities are secured by assets more than twice over.

2. Financial maneuverability and activation of internal reserves. The increase in the maneuverability ratio from a negative value of -0.12 in 2023 to 0.34 in 2025 is a strategically significant result. The negative value indicated that the company's own funds were "tied up" in fixed assets and that there was a shortage of working capital. Under current conditions, however, the enterprise is able to mobilize 34 percent of its equity capital for operational financial activities. This indicates an increased adaptability of the enterprise to changes in market conditions.

3. Optimization of leverage and debt burden. The sharp decline in the debt-to-equity ratio (leverage) from 3.46 to 0.86 represents a fundamental turning point in ensuring the company's financial independence. While in 2023 the company's operations were mainly financed through borrowed funds, by 2025 more than 1.16 soums of equity capital correspond to each soum of debt capital. This situation minimizes the company's risks before creditors and increases its attractiveness for external investment.

4. Growth rate of cash flows. The adequacy of cash flows increased from 12.4 billion soums to 98.6 billion soums, representing nearly an eightfold increase. Such a growth rate proves that the company is not only covering its expenses, but has also created an internal financial source for renewing its technical fleet (purchasing buses) and improving service quality.

The analysis of Table 2 demonstrates that the conceptual mechanism for ensuring financial stability at Toshshahartrans has produced successful results. The enterprise has overcome financial dependence and transformed into a stable economic entity capable of self-financing and systematic development. These indicators guarantee that the company will maintain a positive growth trajectory in the coming years as well.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result of the study on the mechanisms for ensuring financial stability at Toshshahartrans, it can be concluded that the strategic development of the transport sector directly depends on the optimization of capital structure and the level of financial independence. The conducted analysis confirms that during 2023–2025 the enterprise transitioned from a model characterized by high debt dependence to one based on the predominance of stable equity capital. The increase in the autonomy coefficient to the standard level of 0.54 and the multiple growth in profitability indicators demonstrate that the efficiency of financial resource utilization

within the company's management system has reached a significantly higher level. The acceleration of cash flows and the reduction in the turnover period of accounts receivable expanded the company's ability to mobilize internal reserves and minimized the need for external borrowing.

In order to further strengthen financial stability in the enterprise and implement conceptual directions for development in practice, the following proposals were developed:

First of all, it is necessary to fully digitalize the "Financial Risk Early Identification and Monitoring" system within the enterprise. In this regard, it is advisable to introduce a "dashboard of indicators" capable of forecasting negative changes in the capital structure through the use of ERP system capabilities. Such an approach would prevent the emergence of financial "gaps" and increase the speed of operational decision-making.

Secondly, in the process of renewing the transport fleet, it is recommended to shift toward a "mixed financing" model instead of relying solely on leasing or bank loans. In this process, it is possible to maintain the debt burden at a low level by increasing the share of capitalization of net profit and expanding Public-Private Partnership (PPP) mechanisms. This would create an opportunity to use the leverage effect rationally.

Thirdly, it is necessary to apply a strategy of "financial term synchronization" in managing accounts receivable and accounts payable. Ensuring a balance between the timing of cash inflows and payment obligations guarantees the company's absolute liquidity.

As a final recommendation, it is necessary to align the quality of financial management at Toshshahartrans with international standards (IFRS) and to establish the regular implementation of financial stability stress tests. This set of measures will contribute not only to maintaining the company's current stability, but also to shaping it into an economically independent and competitive transport system in the long term. The conceptual directions and analytical conclusions developed in this article may also serve as a methodological foundation for other large enterprises in the sector.

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